

Davao City, Philippines as MICE Destination

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to determine Davao City, Philippines as a Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions (MICE) destination. The research utilized qualitative and quantitative approach. The data were obtained from the delegates of MICE. Adopted and self-made questionnaire was used in this study. The level of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City as MICE is highly satisfied. This means that majority of the respondents were able to have a great experience during the event. Moreover, there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction on the respondents when analyzed according to the sex, age and civil status, while there is a significant difference in terms of educational attainment. This means that the satisfaction of the MICE delegates may differ depending on their educational attainment. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE destination under reliability, empathy, and tangibles. While there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE destination under responsiveness and assurance.*

Keywords: Meetings, Incentive, Conferences, Exhibitions

I. INTRODUCTION

Meetings, Incentives, Conventions, and Exhibitions (MICE) are important aspect of tourism and hospitality industry, it is one of the incomes generating activity, offers different employment opportunities, as well as promotes international linkages. Together with its benefits in the economy are the networking opportunities and collaboration with different sectors (Smagina, 2017). The MICE industry has a big impact in promoting the country's economic status, social relationship, cultural preservation, as it promotes unique differences with each other, with these activities it was able to promote hospitality and tourism activities to the different sectors (Buathong & Lai, 2017). Some of the most attractive and interesting things when it comes to the MICE industry is the different events were able to bring people together, all in the same place for the same purpose and objectives. These activities may be social, formal, or informal type of gathering attended by different people from different place (Choi, Couto, & Immon, 2017). These different events have different needs and wants to come from the organizers and the delegates which refers to the participants of the event (Getz & Page, 2016). An because of these, MICE under tourism and hospitality industry contributes to nations economic growth and as the delegates was able to pay the cost of the event, the organizers must make sure that these delegates are satisfied in the entire experience of the event (Sandy Sou & McCartney, 2015). In recent years, the MICE industry was able to develop an appropriate guideline in delivering quality service to the delegates, this serves as the bases in giving a service to make sure that everything that is being done is based on the standard operating procedure in conducting an event. This guideline includes the area of transportation of the delegates, accessibility of the location, location where the event will be going to happen, and event personnel's who will give the service (Blythe & Martin, 2019). With this it was identifies that there is a need to conduct a study related to the satisfaction of delegates who are attending different MICE events.

The Objective of the study to evaluate Davao City as a Meetings, Incentives, Conventions, and Exhibition's destination. Specifically in terms of the profile of respondents in terms of, sex, age, civil status, educational attainment, and type of event. The level of MICE delegates satisfaction in terms of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. The significant difference in the level of satisfaction when analyzed by profile. Reasons for attending the event. Elements most liked in the event. Information most helpful from the event. Suggestions to improve MICE in Davao City.

Oliver (2014) emphasized customers become satisfied when the expectations were meet. In addition, Zikmund, Babin, Carr, and Griffin (2013) added that satisfaction basically affect and reflects the customer has experienced. If the MICE delegate was able to experience the entire event, then that is the time that there is an assessment whether they are satisfied (Peppers & Rogers 2016). Mohsan et al., (2011) and Atwood (2014); Worley, Williams, and Lawler III (2014) enumerated the different factors that a MICE business can do to achieve customer satisfaction, such as identifying customer expectations and training the employees in giving the best customer experience Recamadas, (2018).

The first indicator in identifying customer satisfaction is reliability; Reliability is an essential factor of customer satisfaction (El Saghier, & Nathan, 2013). Reliability obliged the company to meet promises given to the customers; the positive effect on the business organization is that it reduces uncertainty (Lovelock & Patterson, 2015). In addition,

reliability is all about providing services when promised; also, reliability emphasizes the accordance and continuous, high-quality performance in the business. The organizers of the MICE event must deliver what is being promised to the customers (Nabi, 2012; Galbraith, 2015).

According to Daniel and Berinyuy (2010), the second indicator is customer satisfaction which refers to responsiveness refers to being responsible for all actions taken by the organization; in this case, the organizers of MICE must be responsive in dealing with different concerns of each delegate of the event (Mushi, 2014). It involves timeliness of service, such as attaining customer concerns and giving prompt service (Gemmel, 2017). Responsiveness is all about the MICE event organizer's ability in addressing different situations correction (Nabi, 2012).

The third indicator in measuring customer satisfaction is assurance; it refers to the MICE organizer's ability to decrease possible risk in the MICE event (Singh, Grover & Singh, 2015). Being helpful of the organizers are some of the issues and concerns that all delegates are demanding to address adequately (Nabi, 2012). MICE organizers provide delegates with safety and secured events. (Chao, 2014).

Highlighted by Yulisetiarni (2014), kindness is about caring for individualized attention developed by the business given to every delegates. It is a business strategy that retains customers and develops customer satisfaction (Bourassa, Cunningham, Ashworth & Handelman, 2016). Moreover, Nam and Carnie (2011) added the importance of kindness and proper way of dealing with different delegates concern to make sure that they are being dealt professionally (Wilson et al., 2012).

Tangibles is the last indicator that was significant in attaining customer and Delegate's satisfaction? In MICE industry some of the tangible items refers to the place of the event conducted, and the materials and equipment used in the whole event (Surapranata& Iskandar, 2013).

As MICE industry is becoming one of the new trends in the tourism and hospitality industry, it is very important that each member of the organizing committee must be knowledgeable, skills full enough in dealing with the different concerns of its delegates because this are the factors that basically lead to delegates satisfaction (Pizam, 2016). As Nabi (2012) mentioned, for a company to be tangible, it must be well maintained by the organization; upgrades in the technology used may be a great help in the operation of the business. MICE industry is used by different private and public industries in different gatherings and events.

This study was anchored on the service quality theory of Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml (1988). The idea stated that companies would have more than just a competitive advantage in customer service by having unwavering customer satisfaction. The scale reflects of delegates satisfaction into five constructs as follows: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, the extent to which caring, individualized service is given.

The idea of disconfirmation has its roots in Helson's (1948) adaptation level theory, which suggests that states of satisfaction/dissatisfaction result from comparing one's perception of product performance and one's expectation level (Oliver & Linda, 1981). Several other studies have similarly described the primary mechanism behind the formation of customer satisfaction. According to widely accepted opinion in service research, customer satisfaction will eventually lead to business success (Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1988). With this, said theory was used in the study to identify the level of delegates satisfaction in the MICE industry.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employs descriptive-comparative design, according to Mertens (2014), using this method enables the researchers to gather pertinent data through surveying to determine the results of the study. Selamat (2008) stated that a descriptive survey or normative survey relies on the questions given to the willing participants and later on summarizes the responses with percentages, frequency counts, or more statistical indexes. From these summaries, the researchers draw inferences, conclusions, and findings to the study. Descriptive correlational refers to a type of study in which information is collected without making any changes to the study subject; in addition, descriptive correlation allows examination of the strength of the associations among the variables (Becker, Atinc, Breaugh, Carlson, Edwards, Spector, 2016).Cohen, West, and Aiken (2014) states that quantitative research aims to develop and employ mathematical models, theories, and hypotheses about phenomena. The measurement process is central to quantitative research because it provides the fundamental connection between empirical observation and the mathematical expression of quantitative relationships (Phan & Nguyen, 2016).

The respondents of this were the 300 delegates of meetings, incentives, conventions, and exhibitions in Davao City. This includes the delegates as the respondents of the study since they are the ones who experience the service of different companies that handle events non delegates are excluded in the survey.

In selecting the respondents, a purposive sampling method was employed. It is a non-probability sample determined based on the characteristics of a population and the study's objective (Finch, 2013). A sampling can be beneficial in

situations when there is a need to reach a targeted sample quickly. A piece for proportionality is not the primary concern (Crossman, 2017).

The research instrument is based on the study of Yulisetiari (2014) and Amissah (2012). In addition, the researchers constructed an interview guide questionnaire as the primary source of data. Interviews are a systematic process of conversing with other people. They are also an excellent way for us to immerse ourselves in our research by communicating with the proponents to listen and get their perspectives and experiences as indicated by Jung, Wong, & Zhang (2018). The researchers sought the approval of the panel to conduct the study through a title defense. The researcher sought indicators that correspond to the level of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City as a MICE Destination. Profiles of the respondents are indicated in the questionnaire to know if there is a difference between sex, age, civil status, educational attainment, and type of event. Questionnaires were distributed personally. The researchers set a specific schedule for the time and place of distribution of questionnaires in hotels and event venues in Davao City. Lastly, the questionnaires were retrieved, and data were collected and analyzed. The statistical tools were employed in the treatment of the data. Frequency count was used to determine the exact number of the respondents according to their respective profiles. Percentage was used to determine the exact percentage of the respondents according to their respective profiles. Mean was used to determine the level of cookery competency of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City as a MICE Destination. ANOVA was used to determine the significant difference in the level of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to the educational attainment and age of the respondents.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data. Table 1 represents the profile of respondents; there were 300 total numbers of respondents in the study. In terms of sex, most of the respondents are female, with more than fifty percent of the total respondents, while one hundred seven or thirty-five point seven of the respondents were male. On the other hand, seventy-point seven percent of the respondents were aged twenty to twenty-nine years old or two hundred twelve of the study respondents. Fifty-one respondents came from the thirty to thirty-nine age group or seventeen percent of the respondents. While the remaining twelve-point three percent of the respondents are coming to the age bracket of nineteen below three-point three percent. Forty to forty-nine five percent, and the least number of respondents come from the age bracket sixty above.

In terms of civil status, the majority of the respondents are single; this means that delegates of the different types of events were well participated by single individuals. This is because the majority of the single have more time to participate in other event activities. Meanwhile, one hundred sixteen or thirty-eight point seven are married. This is because there are also married professionals who are also [experienced in different events such as meetings, incentives, conventions, and exhibitions. And the remaining two points, three percent are widowed or widower. Under educational attainment, the majority of the respondents are college graduates, which means that most people who attended different events are professionals. While many delegates are at the college level. At the same time, a small number of respondents are at the high school level and high school graduates.

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

SEX	Frequency	Percent
Male	107	35.7 %
Female	193	64.3 %
AGE		
19 below	10	3.3 %
20 - 29	212	70.7 %
30 - 39	51	17 %
40 -49	15	5 %
50 - 59	10	3.3 %
60 above	2	0.7 %
CIVIL STATUS		
Single	177	59 %
Married	116	38.7 %
Widowed/Widower	7	2.3 %
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT		
High school Level	3	1 %
High school Graduate	4	1.3 %
College Level	46	15.3 %
College Graduate	247	82.3 %
TYPE OF EVENT		
Meeting	62	20.7 %
Incentive	124	41.3 %
Convention	84	28 %
Exhibition	30	10 %
TOTAL	300	100 %

In terms of the type of event, most of the respondents attended the event through incentives. This shows that people in the event industry are experiencing benefits from different companies by sending them to an incentive type of event. Companies see this as an advantage in developing the performance of their employees by giving incentive type of event by sending the top-performing employees to various incentive type of event. On the other hand, eighty-four of the respondents attended a convention type of event; this is also a type of event in which the attendees gather individuals with the same interest. Sixty-two of the respondents attended a meeting, while the remaining thirty respondents or ten percent were into the exhibition. This means that few people attended this kind of event.

Table 2 represents the level of sustainability of delegates in Davao City as a MICE Destination. The indicators of this study are reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, tangibles. In terms of reliability, the MICE organizer can handle the problem faced by delegates has the highest mean with a descriptive level of high satisfaction. This means that the respondents highly agree with the given statement. This shows that the MICE industry in Davao City could cater to different situations that happen in every event. Followed by the promptness of the organizers in serving the delegates is well performed, the order or service transaction process is easy to understand by delegates. When staff promises something by a certain time, it was delivered, and staff can tell when service would be delivered. Everything stated under reliability was able to generate an overall average of delighted. This means that the statements stated under reliability we're able to experience by the respondents.

The result of the study supports the study of Lovelock and Patterson (2015) that the employee's ability to handle different customer problems can basically improve customer satisfaction. In addition, the statement of ElSaghier and Nathan, (2013) about how to attain customer satisfaction state that, every company can consider the different factor on making all employees and personnel know being appropriately performed. Also, Nabi (2012) states that when employees know the operation flow, the proper and correct way of giving the service company will have a smooth operation flow. The company can attain the highest level of customer satisfaction (Galbraith, 2015).

In terms of responsiveness, the highest mean is under the organizers are actively offer easiness in delivering service to their delegates. This means that the MICE industry in Davao City offered to give easy service to the delegates attending different events. Other statements under responsiveness Delegate obtain clear answers related to the facilities of the offered service. Staff telling delegates exactly when service would be performed and when there is a problem, the management response to it quickly also obtained a highly satisfied rating. On the other hand, the statements under organizers can provide a good and friendly answer for delegates to get a satisfying rating. This means that there is a thing that can be improved to deliver better service to the delegates of the MICE industry.

Along with the study conducted by Gemmel (2017), giving a chance to every employee to be responsible for the task given to them will develop a sense of responsibility. On the other hand, Mushi (2014) mentioned that immediate action to every problem encountered by the customer would increase customer satisfaction. While Berinyuy (2010) enumerated acknowledging customer complaints, answering guest queries, performing good service, and being willing to help the customer, every company looks into details to meet customer satisfaction (Nabi, 2012).

On the other side, the assurance items were described the organizers indeed consider their friendliness in providing information for their delegates as the highest mean with a delighted description. This means that the organizers of the MICE industry are friendly to their delegates. Other indicators also got a highly satisfied rating. For instance, organizers are consistently courteous with delegates, delegates feel safe when they are in the event, staff behavior instills confidence in delegates, and delegates feel safe in their transactions. In general, the overall mean under assurance is highly satisfied. This means that the organizers of the different events were able to assure excellent service to the delegates of the MICE industry. Based on the study conducted by Singh, Grover, and Singh (2015), making sure that customers became satisfied with the products and service, companies give assurance by providing clean and safe products and giving safe customer transactions (Chao, 2014). The business establishments make sure that confidentiality and professionalism are observed at all the time (Singh, & Saluja, 2013). Assurance creates a sense of physical impact on customer satisfaction (Yulisetiarni, 2014). Regarding empathy, the item under delegates feels easy to communicate with organizers has the highest mean with a descriptive level of high satisfaction. This means a good relationship between the delegates and the organizers of the MICE industry in Davao City. Other indicators also got a highly satisfied rating. Personnel gives personalized attention to the delegates, delegates feel easy using the offered service organizers, and cares about delegates' needs and wants. The staff gives individual attention to every Delegate in the event.

Sabir et al. (2014) highlighted the importance of accessible communication with the customers to have a better sense of empathy. In the same result with the study Bourassa, Cunningham, Ashworth, and Handelman, (2016) said that

employees should know the needs and wants of the customers even before the customer asks from them. On the contrary, Surapranata and Iskandar (2013) said that companies tend to forget the importance of having individual attention to every customer and giving personalized attention to the guest, leading to customer dissatisfaction (Nam & Carnie, 2011). The last indicator under the level of satisfaction of delegates of MICE in Davao City is the tangibles. The location of the event is easily accessible has the highest satisfaction level with a highly satisfied rating. This means that the accessibility or the place of the event is essential in the success of every event. Another statement also got a highly satisfied rating such as the physical facilities must be visually appealing to the delegates, there must be a parking space to accommodate the vehicles of every Delegate, there should also be a fast internet connection that the delegates can access, and the area of the event must use modern equipment for the event.

Table 2
Level of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City, Philippines as a MICE Destination

ITEM	RELIABILITY	Mean	Descriptive level
R1	The MICE organizer can handle the problem faced by delegates.	4.73	Highly Satisfied
R2	The promptness of the organizers in serving the delegates is well performed.	4.54	Highly Satisfied
R3	The order or service transaction process is easy to understand by delegates.	4.44	Highly Satisfied
R4	When staffs promise something by a certain time, it was delivered.	4.36	Highly Satisfied
R5	Staff can tell when service would be delivered	4.35	Highly Satisfied
Reliability Overall		4.48	Highly Satisfied
ITEM	RESPONSIVENESS		
R1	Organizers are actively offering easiness in delivering service to their delegates.	4.48	Highly Satisfied
R2	Organizers can provide a good and friendly answer to Delegate's complaints.	4.20	Satisfied
R3	Delegates obtain clear answers related to the facilities of the offered service.	4.26	Highly Satisfied
R4	Staff telling delegates exactly when service would be performed.	4.26	Highly Satisfied
R5	When there is a problem, the management respond to it quickly	4.34	Highly Satisfied
Responsiveness Overall		4.31	Highly Satisfied
ITEM	ASSURANCE		
A1	Organizers indeed consider their friendliness in providing information for their delegates.	4.51	Highly Satisfied
A2	Delegates feel safe when they are in the event.	4.29	Highly Satisfied
A3	Staff behavior instills confidence in delegates.	4.28	Highly Satisfied
A4	Delegates feel safe in their transactions.	4.27	Highly Satisfied
A5	Organizers are consistently courteous with delegates	4.31	Highly Satisfied
Assurance Overall		4.33	Highly Satisfied
ITEM	EMPATHY		
E1	Delegates feel easy to communicate with organizers.	4.53	Highly Satisfied
E2	Organizers care about delegates' needs and want.	4.30	Highly Satisfied
E3	Delegates feel easy in using the offered service.	4.31	Highly Satisfied
E4	The staff gives individual attention to every Delegate in the event.	4.30	Highly Satisfied
E5	Personnel gives personalized attention to every Delegate.	4.37	Highly Satisfied
Empathy Overall		4.36	Highly Satisfied
ITEM	TANGIBLES		
T1	The location of the event is easily accessible.	4.55	Highly Satisfied
T2	The parking lot is safe since there are employees who are responsible for and assigned.	4.33	Highly Satisfied
T3	The event uses modern equipment.	4.28	Highly Satisfied
T4	Physical facilities are visually appealing.	4.37	Highly Satisfied
T5	There is a fast internet connection that delegates can access	4.31	Highly Satisfied
Tangibles Overall		4.37	Highly Satisfied

The study's findings were supported by Cantalops and Salvi, (2014), stating that the importance of signage and materials used in operation is as vital as the guide to customer's choice. In addition, Pizam (2016) highlighted the importance of available parking space for the customers. Oliver (2014) also suggested upgrading modern equipment for the company not to be left behind by the other businesses offering the same type of products and services. Considering the different factors that every business sector considers in operating the business, Tan, Oriade, and Fallon (2014) highlighted the importance of small details that sometimes companies don't go into details that is important for meeting customer satisfaction, such as the physical facilities, modern upgraded equipment, and fast internet connection that all customers can access (Jahanshani et al., 2014).

Table 3 shows the significant difference in Delegate's satisfaction on Davao city as a mice destination when analyzed according to sex. The result showed no significant difference between males and females in terms of satisfaction, which means that the null hypothesis was accepted. This serves as a reason that sex does not guarantee whether the person will be satisfied with the services. The findings coincide with the statement of Gemmel (2017), who emphasized that reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles have nothing to do with the sex or gender of the person who receives the service, which means that regardless of male or female the satisfaction will be based on the experience of the person during the actual event itself. This also indicates that for every event type of business, the organizers must focus on service delivery because delivering a good and better experience to all clients and delegates will significantly impact the event's overall performance. In addition, Pizam (2016) added that the event's success depends on the planning and the contribution of every organizer. They are making sure that the needs of delegates are given on time it's needed despite its gender.

Table 3
A significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to sex

	sex	N	Mean	Std. Error Mean
reliability	Male	107	4.4841	0.03885
	Female	193	4.4829	0.02991
responsiveness	Male	107	4.3383	0.04194
	Female	193	4.2922	0.03158
assurance	Male	107	4.3514	0.04079
	Female	193	4.3223	0.03172
Empathy	Male	107	4.357	0.04241
	Female	193	4.3648	0.03308
tangibles	Male	107	4.3495	0.04722
	Female	193	4.3782	0.03506

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	Test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	decision on Ho
reliability	Equal variances assumed	0.003	0.954	0.024	298	0.981	Accept
	Equal variances not assumed			0.025	225.2	0.98	Accept
responsiveness	Equal variances assumed	0.002	0.969	0.875	298	0.382	Accept
	Equal variances not assumed			0.878	221.038	0.381	Accept
assurance	Equal variances assumed	0.362	0.548	0.557	298	0.578	Accept
	Equal variances not assumed			0.564	227.107	0.574	Accept
Empathy	Equal variances assumed	0.161	0.689	-0.142	298	0.887	Accept
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.144	227.702	0.885	Accept
Tangibles	Equal variances assumed	0.041	0.84	-0.488	298	0.626	Accept
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.488	218.442	0.626	Accept

The significant difference in Delegate's satisfaction on Davao city as a mice destination when analyzed according to age. No significant difference was found on the indicators as follows for reliability the significant difference of 0.959, which means that the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as MICE destination in terms of reliability. Regarding responsiveness, the significant difference is 0.458, which means that there is no significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction of MICE industry in terms of responsiveness.

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In the remaining three indicators, a significant difference of 0.619 for assurance of 0.987 for empathy and 0.331 for tangibles also has the same result, meaning there is no significant difference in the level of delegates satisfaction in attending different MICE in Davao City.

Table 4

A significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
reliability	Between Groups	0.178	5	0.036	0.209	0.959	Accept
	Within Groups	50.099	294	0.17			
	Total	50.277	299				
responsiveness	Between Groups	0.894	5	0.179	0.936	0.458	Accept
	Within Groups	56.164	294	0.191			
	Total	57.057	299				
assurance	Between Groups	0.667	5	0.133	0.707	0.619	Accept
	Within Groups	55.532	294	0.189			
	Total	56.2	299				
empathy	Between Groups	0.129	5	0.026	0.125	0.987	Accept
	Within Groups	60.838	294	0.207			
	Total	60.967	299				
tangibles	Between Groups	1.368	5	0.274	1.157	0.331	Accept
	Within Groups	69.525	294	0.236			
	Total	70.893	299				

The study's findings supported Galbraith's (2015) statement, stating that the importance of customer satisfaction cannot be dismissed because happy customers, despite age race, are like free advertising. The high-quality relationship with customers is the primary influence of a successful service provider (Mohsan et al., 2011).

Atwood (2014); Worley, Williams, and Lawler III (2014) enumerated the different factors that a business can do to achieve customer satisfaction, such as identifying and relying on reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. These indicators are critical in attaining a successful business operation. The study shows that age does not matter on the level of satisfaction given to the delegates of the MICE industry in Davao City.

In terms of the significant difference under civil status represents the significant difference in Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Civil Status. In terms of reliability, there is a significant difference of 0.813 with means that the null hypothesis was accepted, also, in the area of responsiveness with a p-value of 0.275, which also means that there is also no significant difference in the level of delegates satisfaction of different MICE events in terms of responsiveness.

The assurance area between civil status has a significant value of 0.068, which accepted the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the level of delegates' satisfaction in terms of assurance. The remaining two indicators, empathy with a p-value of 0.222 and tangibles with a p-value of 0.723, have the same result of no significant difference between delegates satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE-destination when analyzed according to the civil status of the respondents.

The result of the study reveals that the person's civil status does not guarantee satisfaction with the service that is given. Therefore, even if the person is single or married, it does not relate to the satisfaction or level of satisfaction to the event. This also shows that the satisfaction of the delegates that attended different events in Davao City will be based on the experience that they encounter during the actual event that happened.

That is why every event organizer must make sure that the flow or program of the event is well planned and organized to make sure that the event will become successful, even if the different attendees are coming from different races or civil statuses. What matters most is the event itself. The event's success will always matter most because it's what the delegates are always looking for.

Table 5
A significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Civil Status

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
reliability	Between Groups	0.07	2	0.035	0.208	0.813	Accept
	Within Groups	50.206	297	0.169			
	Total	50.277	299				
responsiveness	Between Groups	0.494	2	0.247	1.296	0.275	Accept
	Within Groups	56.564	297	0.19			
	Total	57.057	299				
assurance	Between Groups	1.006	2	0.503	2.708	0.068	Accept
	Within Groups	55.193	297	0.186			
	Total	56.2	299				
empathy	Between Groups	0.614	2	0.307	1.511	0.222	Accept
	Within Groups	60.353	297	0.203			
	Total	60.967	299				
tangibles	Between Groups	0.155	2	0.077	0.324	0.723	Accept
	Within Groups	70.738	297	0.238			
	Total	70.893	299				

Customer Satisfaction is an emotional or feeling reaction regardless of the civil status of the person (Oliver, 2014). It is the result of a complex process that requires understanding the psychology of customers. The range of emotion is wide, for example, surprise, pleasure, contentment, or relief (Jahanshani et al., 2014). Satisfaction is influenced, in the end, by my expectations and the gap between perceived qualities and expected quality, called expectancy disconfirmation (Tan, Oriade, & Fallon, 2014). In addition, customer satisfaction is the highest form of customer service (Cantalops & Salvi, 2014). Many businesses are trying hard to identify and attain the highest possible way to satisfy the customers and eventually become loyal to the company (Nejad, Firoozbakht, & Taghipoor, 2014).

Table 6
A significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Educational Attainment

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
reliability	Between Groups	1.974	3	0.658	4.032	0.008	Reject
	Within Groups	48.303	296	0.163			
	Total	50.277	299				
responsiveness	Between Groups	3.135	3	1.045	5.737	0.001	Reject
	Within Groups	53.922	296	0.182			
	Total	57.057	299				
assurance	Between Groups	2.341	3	0.78	4.289	0.006	Reject
	Within Groups	53.859	296	0.182			
	Total	56.2	299				
empathy	Between Groups	2.112	3	0.704	3.541	0.015	Reject
	Within Groups	58.854	296	0.199			
	Total	60.967	299				
tangibles	Between Groups	3.459	3	1.153	5.061	0.002	Reject
	Within Groups	67.434	296	0.228			
	Total	70.893	299				

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable	(I) Educational	(J) Educational	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
responsiveness	5	6	-.26851*	0.06854	0.002	-0.4612	-0.0758
tangibles	5	6	-.26270*	0.07665	0.009	-0.4782	-0.0472

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 6 represents the significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Educational Attainment in terms of reliability; the significant difference is 0.008, which means that the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination in terms of reliability; the data also shows that the person's educational attainment is a factor in identifying the satisfaction level in terms of attending different MICE events. Under responsiveness, the significant difference is 0.001, which means that the null hypothesis was rejected; this means that there is a significant difference in the level of delegates' satisfaction attending the Event in Davao City in terms of responsiveness.

The other remaining indicators also got the same result for assurance 0.006 for empathy 0.015, and tangibles are 0.002. This means that all indicators under significant difference in the level of delegates satisfaction regarding educational attainment were rejected. This means a significant difference in the level of tourist satisfaction in Davao City as a MICE-destination when analyzed according to the respondents' educational attainment.

Considering the different factors that every business sector identified in operating the business, Tan, Oriade, and Fallon (2014) highlighted the importance of delegates of MICE industry that sometimes companies don't go into details such as the educational attainment of the delegates who will attend the event which is essential for meeting customer satisfaction, such as the physical facilities, modern upgraded equipment, and fast internet connection that all customer can access (Jahanshani et al., 2014). The study also shows that since most of the respondents attending an event are college graduates or professionals, quality service is essential because they can quickly identify and distinguish good quality service. Since the majority of the people from this industry are well educated, the respondents and delegates must be given quality service to attain high customer satisfaction.

Table 7
A significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
reliability	Between Groups	2.31	3	0.77	4.751	0.003	Reject
	Within Groups	47.967	296	0.162			
	Total	50.277	299				
responsiveness	Between Groups	1.421	3	0.474	2.52	0.058	Accept
	Within Groups	55.637	296	0.188			
	Total	57.057	299				
assurance	Between Groups	1.305	3	0.435	2.345	0.073	Accept
	Within Groups	54.895	296	0.185			
	Total	56.2	299				
empathy	Between Groups	1.779	3	0.593	2.966	0.032	Reject
	Within Groups	59.188	296	0.2			
	Total	60.967	299				
tangibles	Between Groups	3.267	3	1.089	4.767	0.003	Reject
	Within Groups	67.626	296	0.228			
	Total	70.893	299				

Multiple Comparisons

Scheffe

Dependent Variable	(I) Event	(J) Event	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
reliability	1	3	-.22035*	0.0674	0.015	-0.4099	-0.0308
tangibles	1	2	-.25645*	0.07435	0.009	-0.4655	-0.0474
tangibles	1	3	-.26644*	0.08003	0.012	-0.4915	-0.0414

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Davao City, Philippines as MICE Destination

Displays the significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event in terms of reliability the significant difference is 0.003, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected this means that there is a significant difference in the level of delegates satisfaction on Davao City as MICE destination when analyzed according to the type of event under reliability this also means that there is a difference between The MICE organizers ability to handle the problem faced by delegates. The promptness of the organizers in serving the delegates is well performed. Order or service transaction process is easy to understand by delegates, staff's ability to deliver what is promised, and staff ability to tell when service would be delivered.

In terms of responsiveness, the p-value is 0.058, and the significant assurance difference is 0.073 both accepted the hypothesis this means that there is no significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event in terms of responsiveness and assurance.

Lastly, in terms of empathy which has a significant difference of 0.032 and tangibles 0.003, the null hypothesis was rejected. This also means a significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event under empathy and tangibles. This means that there is a difference in the area of delegates feel easy to communicate with organizers, organizers care about delegates' needs and want, delegates feel easy in using the offered service, the staff gives individual attention to every Delegate in the event, personnel give personalized attention to every Delegate under empathy. The event's location is easily accessible. The parking lot is safe since there are employees responsible for and assigned. The event uses modern equipment, physical facilities are visually appealing, and there is a fast internet connection that delegates can access under tangibles. This means that responsiveness and assurance have no significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event. In contrast, reliability, empathy, and tangibles have a significant difference in the level of Delegate's satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE Destination when analyzed according to Type of Event.

Reasons for attending the event.

When the delegates were asked concerning choosing to attend the event, the participants gave their opinion on the matter as follows:

It provides me incredible experience and opportunities for learning (P2, P5, P6). For Professionalism (P1, P5). To find solutions to my problem with the project (P4, P6). The majority of the participants highlighted choosing to attend the event that provides fantastic experience and opportunities in Davao City as MICE-destination. Meeting, Incentive, Convention, Conference, and Exhibition attendants currently spend the most on lodging, followed by the registration costs (Fenich, 2016). Thus, accommodation cost influences attendees' lodging experience and, in turn, the total experience in attending an event. As the competition increases, it will become more critical for destinations and conference facilities to recognize factors that affect event planners' site selection decisions and place their services appropriately in the market. Researchers are keen to assess the overall ranks and the relative attractiveness of major MICE destinations. Factors that contribute to the competence of these MICE destinations were also analyzed extensively. However, a detailed analysis of the literature on the competitiveness of destinations found that the picture of a MICE destination as viewed by delegates was often calculated to assess and decide the competitiveness of MICE destinations as mentioned by Kim, Yoon, & Kim (2011). In conditioning the mind of the delegates to their preference, perception is deemed more important than fact (So, Li & Lehto, 2011). Therefore, the selection process for the site is a significant component of the MICE industry and involves three leading players: meeting vendors, meeting buyers, and attendants (Hayat, Severt, Breiter, Nusair & Okumus, 2014).

For this reason, attending the MICE delegates in Davao City, the delegates considered developing network or business relationship, safety and cleanness, and knowledge as the first tier of reasons, simultaneously attaching slight importance to gaming, shopping, and entertainment (Qiu, Li, So, S.-I, & Lehto, 2015). Thus, topic and theme of the MICE is the most important factor that attracts delegates to organized in Davao City, followed by network development and professional knowledge update.

Elements most liked in the event.

Concerning which element of the event, the delegates will attend the meeting, incentive, conference, convention, and exhibition. The delegates express their various perspective as follows:

Place, very accessible to all establishment's venue is at the heart of the city (P1, P2, P4), price. It is budget-friendly and worth the Price (P2), people, very accommodating and very good in service (P3), product, their food, and service are good (P4). The delegates mainly emphasized the accessibility of the venue's location, which is the city's heart where the establishment, theme parks, churches, transportation, or any other destinations are accessible to the delegates. Accessibility is considered a significant factor when selecting a location for a meeting, incentive, convention, conference, and exhibition (Lee & Lee, 2017). Sanders (2004) mentions that a positive picture of delegates and conference destinations draws more delegates and raises the average ratio of hotel room night's attendants.

Likewise, organizers should evaluate a venue as to how its brand will help attract the delegates and exhibitors and promote branding for exhibitions and meetings, and conferences. A center band developed over time through past organizer experiences and other organizer testimonials are central to a hotel and convention centers selection process.

Information most helpful from the event. The delegates were inquired concerning about usefulness of the information presented during the conduct of MICE in Davao City; they respond as follows:

The information is beneficial to gather new ideas (P2, P4, and P6)....Most delegates are expected the fact that evaluations are undertaken for a range of reasons: evaluating the importance of existing programs and measuring the usefulness of attempts to improve them, determining the effectiveness of program management and administration, and satisfying the accountability requirements of the program (Pearlman & Morelle, 2009). MICE delegates explore business opportunities and update customer awareness by evaluating and comparing the items on offer (Qui et al., 2015). Hence, the delegates of the MICE are mainly company representatives. On the contrary, MICE attendees get together to exchange ideas, build connections, and discuss specific critical issues. They are often in the same organization, association, or corporation but occasionally meet one another. Therefore, it is now the time to contribute more to this area from the MICE perspective. The basic methodology to study the MICE destination competitiveness applies to the MICE industry (Kim, Sun & Ap, 2008).

Suggestions to improve MICE in Davao City. When the delegates inquire about what would have made the event better as a MICE destination in Davao City, the delegates retorted as follows:

It would be better if everybody will cooperate (P1, P3, P4, P5). Comfortable and affordable (P1, P2, P5). As mentioned by Whitfield, Dioko, Webber & Zhang (2014) developed the powerful attributes that contribute to the tendency of MICE delegates to attend an exhibition held at a MICE complex venue. Their study indicated that attributes of destination level remain the most significant, particularly in terms of destination climate, reputation, infrastructure, and safety for the betterment of the MICE conducted.

The delegates were asked to give comments and suggestions enable to improve the Meeting, Incentive, Conference, Convention, and Exhibition in Davao City; the delegates respond as follow:

More promotions on the venue per establishment to attract clients/tourists to have their event here in our city and also affordable one (P2, P5, P6). The MICE industry usually features high-expenditure delegates and opportunities for local businesses and jobs (Wu, 2014). Seeing those potential profits and benefits, most countries worldwide are now involved in the business of MICE as a destination or as a demanding market (Llambi, 2005).

IV. CONCLUSION

The level of satisfaction of delegates in Davao City as a MICE-destination regarding reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles is delightful. There is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE-destination when analyzed according to sex, age, civil status, and civil status of the respondents. There is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE-destination when analyzed according to the respondents' Educational Attainment. Regarding the type of event, there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction in Davao City as a MICE-destination under reliability, empathy, and tangibles. At the same time, there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction on Davao City as a MICE-destination under responsiveness and assurance.

Majority of the proponents choose to attend the event because it provides them beautiful experiences and opportunities for learning. The element of the event which the delegates like the most is the price and place because the event is affordable and accessible. In information in the event is very useful in gathering new ideas. The event can be made better if everybody will cooperate. Promotions are one way to improve the MICE events in Davao City.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were drawn based on the initial results of the study of the satisfaction of MICE delegates.

Cooperation and teamwork must develop in different personnel involved in the meetings, expositions, conventions, and exhibitions. This can be developed by team-building activities as well as seminars and training on cooperation and teamwork. For each member of the organization to understand the critical role of each member of the group.

The organizers of different MICE events may add more marketing strategies to promote the different events in Davao City. An online marketing tool can be an effective, efficient, and affordable way of doing a marketing activity. It is also known to be easy and accessible to everyone in the MICE industry because the organizers can now reach out to delegates worldwide using an online marketing advertisement.

Organizers of the Event may improve the excellent and friendly answer to the delegates' training in personality development. This can be done by continuous professional development under a personality development program that will enhance the customer service relationship skills of the organizers of the MICE industry.

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